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The Growth of Women's Education in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

A country's foundation is its educational system. Without education, no country can advance since it teaches knowledge and abilities that improve quality of life and human growth. Women's education is essential to society and to a country. Investment in preparing the workforce of the future is very essential in a developing nation like Bangladesh, which is one of the most promising emerging economies. Education is a fundamental human right, but in a developing country like Bangladesh, special focus must be placed on the education of women. Women who pursue education will not only have higher household incomes and help create a more skilled labor force, but they will also have greater social mobility. The value of education to our nation cannot be overstated. Therefore, government should focus more on the issue. Given that women make up half of our population, this essay will examine the situation of women's education in Bangladesh. This investigation into the advancement of women's education and the resources made available by the Bangladeshi government was carried out through the analysis of documents. It will encourage researchers to look further into the education and development of women.

INTRODUCTION

Statement of the Problem

Bangladesh is a large, low-income country with a young, largely illiterate population, especially among women and the poor. According to recent estimates for the population over the age of 11, 35.6 percent of women are literate, compared to 47.6 percent of men (Ahmaed *et al.*, 2005). According to Ahmaed *et al.* (2007), there are around 150,000 institutions, 760 000 professors, and one million students enrolled in all levels of education up to the university. Education in Bangladesh is also characterized by a high degree of administrative centralization and the use of women as teachers. Despite systemic improvements since 1990, socioeconomic inequality and the rural-urban split still exist. 18 million kids are enrolled in one of four major types of primary education. According to Ahmaed *et al.* (2009), the net primary enrolment rate grew from 82.0 percent in 1996 to 89.7 percent in 2004. (Over these year the rate for boys went from 83.0 to 84.0 percent, while that for girls increased from 81.0 to 96.0 percent). Despite the increased enrollment in these games, there are still significant shortcomings in the quality of the learning results and completion rates.

According to Ahmaed *et al.* (2006), 48% of children who enroll in elementary school leave before completing the five-year cycle. Education is a fundamental human right and a means of attaining peace, progress, and equality. Men and women both gain from nondiscriminatory education, which ultimately equalizes interactions between the sexes. Giving the female population more than just a basic education is one way to empower women, which is one of the key components of effective social and economic development in today's society. Women must have equal access to educational opportunities if they are to be

change agents. Reduced fertility, improved nutrition, and poverty are all benefits of female education. Education increases women's chances of participating in formal paid jobs, their ability to influence family decisions, and their personal health outcomes and life expectancy. Aside from the intrinsic importance of education, women with greater levels of education are more productive, earn more money, marry later, and produce fewer, healthier, and more intelligent children. Education increases a woman's involvement in civic issues. The ability of an educated woman to escape the poverty cycle is maybe of utmost importance. Instead, she can take part in a good educational cycle that secures the prosperity of her offspring and her nation. A study that quantified their contributions found that a rise in female educational attainment increases the real GDP per capita's subsequent growth rate. According to the projection, every additional year of education for women increases growth by between two and four percent annually. The advantages are so great that many experts are of the opinion that investing in the education of women may likely yield the highest returns in the developing countries. In a nutshell, Bangladesh is a developing country and behind her les and slow development lack of proper female education is one of the causes.

Methods

This paper relied on secondary sources of data which include books, journals, previous studies, government documents, newspapers and periodicals. A qualitative data analysis technique was employed in order to analyze data.

Theoretical Framework

This paper clarifies the concept of education and women

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empowerment. It also examines the gap between the literacy level of male gender and that of the female gender.

Objective of the Study

1. To be aware of female education in order to combat poverty, early marriage, women's abuse, etc.
2. To determine the number of educated women and prepare them to contribute to the social and economic development of the nation.
3. To understand the social standing of women in the neighborhood, lessen gender inequality, and boost population growth.
4. To understand the importance of female education and the overall advancement of women's empowerment.
5. To inspire women by portraying a realistic image of female education and its future.
6. To offer suggestions for improving the current system.

Scope of the Study

Our nation's educational system recognizes the value of female education. The advancement of the nation depends on female education. Therefore, one of the crucial challenges in the context of Bangladesh is to do a detailed study on women's education. Here, efforts have been made to identify the issues and future opportunities relating to female education. Most female students stop attending school after or before completing high school. Numerous factors, such as poverty, early marriage, the absence of parents, an inadequate stipend, the load of family duties, a lack of stability, and others, contribute to their dropping out. Consequently, this paper's scope is quite broad. Due to the time and opportunity constraints, all aspects of the study on female education could not be included.

Status of Bangladesh Literacy Rate in South Asia

Investment in preparing the workforce of the future is very essential in a developing nation like Bangladesh, which is one of the most promising emerging economies. The second Millennium Development Goal of the United Nations aims to achieve universal primary education (MDG). However, studies show that Bangladesh's enrollment rates in school, for both genders, give the impression that the country is far behind its peers. For instance, Sri Lanka has the highest literacy rate in South Asia at 92% as of 2016. India has a literacy rate of 74%. As of 2016, Bangladesh has a literacy rate of 70%, which is comparable to India's but vastly different from Bangladesh's. It is important to consider the stark differences in economic aspects, such as population, for example. Because of this, the trend in the proportion of official development assistance (ODA) going to the Bangladeshi education sector can be worrisome. This will put the need for more focus on our education sector into better perspective.

Education is a fundamental human right, but in a

developing country like Bangladesh, special focus must be placed on the education of women. Rural families frequently avoid enrolling their young girls in school because they feel that women are only suited for household management. It is concerning to hold such a view in 2016, which is why our nation's educational system urgently needs some improvements.

It is crucial to raise young girls in our nation to be educated ladies. A cost-benefit analysis will show that the benefits are greater than the costs. The number of child brides in Bangladesh will decline first and foremost. As a result, the national average age at which women become pregnant will increase, ensuring that the health of the mother and the unborn child is not jeopardized. These people will have certain talents as a result of their primary education, which can serve as a foundation for later specialized skill acquisition. When women eventually decide to have children, they are more likely to understand the value of education and to make sure that their children receive an education as well. The most important thing is these women will not discriminate between their sons and daughters, if they had grown up being treated the same as their brothers.

Women who pursue education will not only have higher household incomes and help create a more skilled labor force, but they will also have greater social mobility. They have advanced in social class as a result of positive vertical social mobility. Men are predicted to refrain from using domestic violence, while women are more likely to be able to deal with domestic violence at home, should there be any. This is expected if the education sector can offer sufficient instruction to both sexes equally. In the long run, this will promote women's self-esteem, raise their status, and make them happier and more self-assured.

Every person living in poverty dreams of breaking free from the cycle of poverty, and education is the means by which this desire might be transformed. However, international assistance to Bangladesh's education system has decreased. In Bangladesh, aid to education increased from USD 148 million in 2002–2003 to USD 528 million in 2013. This amount decreased to USD 449 million in 2014. In Bangladesh, aid for elementary education was 19 USD per child in 2013, while in 2014, it was 13 USD per child. This compares favorably to Sri Lanka (\$25/child) and Afghanistan (\$50/child) in 2014.

It is evident that foreign aid to education can result in significant improvements, yet despite the anticipated results, aid to education is currently smaller than it was the previous year. The value of education to our nation cannot be overstated. Therefore, government should focus more on the issue.

BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Literacy Rate: Youth Aged 15-24

Literacy Rate: Youth Aged 15-24 data was reported at 1.028 Ratio in 2020. BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Literacy Rate. This is an increase over the prior figure for 2019 of 1.025 Ratio. BD: Youth Aged 15-24 Literacy

Rate data is updated yearly, with a Ratio of 1.028 from December 1981 to 2020 and 15 observations. The ratio of the data ranged from a record high of 1.196 in 2007 to a record low of 0.612 in 1981. BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Literacy Rate: Youth Aged 15-24 data is supplied by the World Bank and has an active status in CEIC.

The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD.World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The ratio of girls to males aged 15 to 24 who can read and write with comprehension a brief, simple statement about their daily lives is known as the gender parity index for youth literacy rates (UIS).

Figure 1: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Literacy Rate: Youth Aged 15-24

BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Primary and Secondary School Enrollment

Primary and secondary school enrollment for the BD Gender Parity Index (GPI): Gross data was reported at 1.135 Ratio in 2021. This is a decline from the prior value for 2020 of 1.146 Ratio. BD: Primary and Secondary School Enrollment: Gender Parity Index (GPI) Averaging 0.740 Ratio across 24 observations from December 1973 to December 2021, gross data is updated yearly. The ratio of the data ranged from a record low of 0.499 Ratio in 1976 to an all-time high of 1.146 Ratio in 2020.

Primary and Secondary School Enrollment: Gross data remains active status in CEIC and is supplied by World Bank. BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD.World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The ratio of girls to boys enrolled at the elementary and secondary levels in public and private schools is known as the gender parity index for gross enrolment ratio in primary and secondary education (UIS). Bulk Data Download Service by UIS.Stat. 24th October 2022 access date.

Figure 2: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Primary and Secondary School Enrollment

BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI): Tertiary School Enrollment:

Tertiary School Enrollment: Gross data was recorded at 0.833 Ratio in 2021. BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI) This represents an improvement over the prior figure of 0.812

Ratio for 2020. Tertiary School Enrollment: BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI) The average Ratio for the Gross data from December 1970 to December 2021, with 38 observations, was 0.484. The data peaked in 2021 at 0.833 Ratio and hit a record low in 1970 of 0.113 Ratio. Tertiary

School Enrollment: Gross data has a current active status in CEIC and is provided by the World Bank. BD: Gender Parity Index (GPI). The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD.World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The ratio of women to men enrolled at the tertiary level in public and private schools is known as the gender parity index for gross enrollment ratio in tertiary education (UIS). Bulk Data Download Service by UIS.Stat. 24th October 2022 access date.

BD: Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education:

Female: % of Relevant Age Group statistics for BD: Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education was reported at 109.285% in 2018. This represents an

increase from the prior figure for 2017 of 105.792%. The data for BD: Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education: Female: % of Relevant Age Group is updated yearly and includes 14 observations with a mean value of 111.713% from December 1976 to 2018. The data peaked in 2011 at 130.035% and hit a record low in 1976 at 84.095%. The World Bank continues to report data on the Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education: Female: % of Relevant Age Group. The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD. World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The number of new students entering the first grade of primary education, regardless of age, is referred to as the gross intake ratio and is calculated by the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (<http://uis.unesco.org/>).

Figure 3: Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education

BD: Lower Secondary Completion Rate: Female

2017 data for the BD: Lower Secondary Completion Rate: Female: % of Relevant Age Group indicated a figure of 74.341%. This represents a reduction from the prior figure for 2016 of 87.128%. The data for BD: Lower Secondary Completion Rate: Female: % of Relevant Age Group is updated monthly and includes 16 observations with a mean of 61.838% from Dec 1998 to 2017. The information peaked at 87.128% in 2016 and fell to a record low of 51.636% in 1998. Lower Secondary Completion Rate: Female: % of Relevant Age Group data is supplied by World Bank and has an active status

in CEIC. The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD.World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The gross intake ratio to the final grade of lower secondary education is used to calculate the completion rate for this level of education (general and pre-vocational).

It is computed by dividing the population at the admission age for the last grade of lower secondary school by the number of new students entering that grade, regardless of age. UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). Bulk Data Download Service by UIS.Stat. 24th October 2022 access date.

Figure 3: Gross Intake Ratio in First Grade of Primary Education

BD: Adolescents Out of School: Female

According to the 2017 data from BD: Adolescents Out of School: Female: % of Female Lower Secondary School Age, this percentage was 25.432%. There has been a decline from the prior figure for 2016 of 27.734%. The data for BD: Adolescents Out of School: Female: % of Female Lower Secondary School Age is updated yearly and includes 9 observations with a 9-year average growth of 26.159%. The data peaked in 2014 at 33.551% and hit a record low in 2010 at 12.433%. World Bank

reports the BD: Adolescents Out of School: Female: % of Female Lower Secondary School Age data, which has an active status in CEIC. The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD. World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The proportion of teenagers in lower secondary school who are not enrolled in school is known as the “adolescent out of school” rate (UIS). Bulk Data Download Service by UIS.Stat. 24th October 2022 access date.

Figure 5: Adolescents Out of School: Female

BD: Literacy Rate: Adult Female

According to data from BD: Adult Female Literacy Rate: % of Females Aged 15 and above, it was 72.005% in 2020. This represents an improvement for 2019 above the prior figure of 71.948%. The data for BD: Literacy Rate: Adult Female: % of Females Aged 15 and above is updated monthly, with 14 observations between Dec 1981 and 2020 with an average of 57.825%. In 2020, the statistics hit an all-time high of 72.005%, and in 1981, it hit a record low of 17.972%. BD: Adult Female Literacy

Rate: % of Females Aged 15 and Above data is supplied by the World Bank and has an active status in CEIC. The information is arranged under Bangladesh - Table BD.World Bank in the Global Database. WDI: Social: Statistics on Education. The percentage of adults aged 15 and older who can read and write and comprehend a brief, straightforward statement about their daily lives is known as the adult literacy rate (UIS). Bulk Data Download Service by UIS.Stat. 24th October 2022 access date.

Figure 6: Literacy Rate: Adult Female

Female Education in Bangladesh

No citizen of Bangladesh may be subject to any prohibition, restriction, or unfair treatment with regard to admission to any educational institution on the basis

of sex, according to the constitution of that country. The constitution also gives the state the authority to create particular protections for women. It has long been accepted in official circles that education helps

girls become better mothers and wives. After gaining independence in 1974, the newly elected government met with the Qudrat-e-Khuda Education Commission to discuss the most important aspects of education policy. The commission report framed women's education as beneficial to traditional gender roles and family life. The panel made connections between female education and outcomes like children, health and nutrition, and acceptable professions like teaching and nursing (Jalauddin and Chowdhury, 1997). Since then, aside from a more recent focus on population control, most initiatives intended to encourage girls' education have tended to adhere to these objectives.

Bangladesh's policy on girls' education have taken into account the fact that some parents are hesitant to support their daughters' education. Parents may conclude that investing in their daughter's education is not a wise use of their limited resources in this patriarchal society when daughters marry into other families (Raynor, 20005). With poverty, this inclination gets worse.

In the sub-sector as a whole, and frequently unnoticed, institutions and schools have not benefited from supervision received, there is an acute teacher shortage in many schools, some teachers are not well-prepared for their jobs, schools and students lack enough learning materials, physical facilities are insufficient for the number of students requiring access to education, and instructional time is insufficient. In a short amount of time, all these flaws must be fixed.

Problems of Female Education

International Women's Day, or IWD, is observed annually on March 8 based on the circumstance and a theme decided upon by the United Nations (UN). As in previous years, the subject for this year's celebration is "Women in leadership: Achieving an equal future in a COVID-19 world." This year's day aims to draw attention to the crucial role that women have been playing as health professionals, carers, and innovators in communities around the world.

If they are not given the assurance of a trouble- and risk-free education in the nation, women's leadership cannot be attained. Due to extreme inequality and differences in educational systems, women's access to school has been severely restricted during the pandemic. In Bangladesh, women are stereotyped as pursuing a family-centered existence, which worsens the nation's reputation while also keeping education at a standstill until the illiteracy age.

Therefore, it is crucial to raise young girls in our nation to be intelligent ladies. A cost-benefit analysis will show that the benefits are greater than the costs. Education for women is a top objective for strategic development. Should they decide to become mothers, women with higher levels of education typically have fewer children, marry later in life, and their children are typically healthier. They also tend to be more knowledgeable about nutrition and healthcare. They have a better probability

of participating in the formal job market and earning more money. Combining all of these elements can aid in eradicating poverty from households, communities, and entire nations.

In order to eliminate the obstacles girls, confront when pursuing their education, preventive measures must be adopted. First and foremost, small-scale community projects should inform locals and residents in impoverished areas of the value of girls' education. This will make gender equality easier for the underprivileged to understand. Second, males should be taught the value of gender equality and the enormous social impact that education for women may have. Finally, laws must be enforced more strictly, both on roadways and in classrooms. Regarding the safety of girls, schools must have strict guidelines that must be followed at all times. In order to secure the safety of drivers, more security people, such as police officers, must be stationed in various parts of the route.

The establishment of madrasa schools has been one of the most effective strategies to guarantee women's education in Bangladesh. Children who attend a madrasas school can receive both civil and religious education, which gives parents the peace of mind to send their daughters to school without worrying that their religious convictions will be violated. More girls are able to enroll in school thanks to the growth of madrasas schools that serve more religious families and communities.

On the basis of the aforementioned explanation, we may draw the conclusion that women's access to education not only boosts household earnings and helps create a more skilled labor force, but also increases their social mobility and ensures the quality of education in the nation. There must be a better world to lead the country and achieve future equality in the world if the education sector can offer good education to both sexes equally, men are expected not to resort to domestic violence, and women are more likely to overcome the condition of domestic violence at home. Additionally, this will promote women's pride, raise their stature, and ultimately make them happier and more self-assured.

Some of the obstacles women face in acquiring education are mentioned below:

1. Poverty:
 - a) Women's access to education is hampered by poverty.
 - b) Poor parents deprive their daughters of an education.
2. Early Marriage: -
 - a) Guardians believe that if a woman is older, they won't find a suitable spouse.
 - b) The guardians' limited financial resources.
 - c) Less capable female students are married off.
3. Unawareness of Guardians: -
 - a) Illiterate Guardians always make disparaging remarks about women's education.
 - b) They believe that women won't be of any future assistance.
4. Disparity in religious beliefs:
 - a) The majority of families oppose female education

due to their beliefs.

b) Some parents believed that highly educated women couldn't adequately participate in religious activities.

c) Because of religious discrimination, many intelligent people are unable to finish their studies.

5. Communication system:

a) The majority of women are illiterate due to communication system.

b) Girls also can't go far to get to school.

c) A failure to communicate Roads are another factor in the undereducation of women.

6. Issues with housing:

a) lack of housing options makes it difficult for majority of women to continue their education.

b) Female students who lack protection are made losers for pursuing their education.

7. Causes of Eve-Teasing:

a) Eve-teasing has a significant role today in the demise of female education;

b) Eve-teasing affects women of all ages, which contributes to the daily decline in female enrollment in educational institutions.

8. Lack of Security:

a) Security concerns prevent the majority of women from continuing their education.

b) Parents of women who stay in hostels experience a lack of security.

c) Women experience insecurities when communicating in public settings like buses and trains. so that their parents won't consent to go to long distant places.

Growth of Women's Education in Bangladesh

Many authors stress the importance of education for women's emancipation. According to Islam (2010), women who lack education also lack self-confidence. Naturally, an educated woman will have a variety of problem-solving and decision-making skills, and she will want to put those to use for herself and her family. The National Education Policy of Bangladesh¹⁵ (2010) placed a strong emphasis on encouraging women's education across the board in order to do away with any sex-based stereotyping and guarantee equality. In order to secure women's holistic growth, empowerment, and involvement in societal advancement, the policy has also placed a strong emphasis on women's education. A number of measures for women's education have been taken by Bangladesh's succeeding governments. As a result, women now have higher educational levels. The gender gap in this industry has greatly shrunk as a result of affirmative action measures adopted in the allocation of financial resources in the education sector and women-friendly education regulations. According to the Population Census-2001 of Bangladesh, the literacy rate for people aged 7 and older increased from around 26% to 45.32% over the course of the previous 20 years (1981–2001). It hits 56.1 percent in 2011.

The remarkable increase in women's education during this time has made a significant contribution to Bangladesh's

improvement in its literacy rate. Girls' secondary school enrollment has increased significantly during the 1980s, from 39% in 1998 to 67% in 2017. The Female Secondary School Assistance Project (FSSAP), which was launched in the early 1990s initially as a trial and later as a statewide initiative, was particularly important in attaining gender equality and is the cause of this progress.

According to data from the 2017 Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information and Statistics, girls' secondary school dropout rates are at a high 42 percent. Completion rates are also low, with grade 10 completion rates bottoming out at just 10 percent and secondary level completion rates only rising to 59 percent.

The most alarming scenario is that female students drop out at a higher rate than male pupils. In terms of completion rate, dropout rate, and survival rate, there is a significant difference between male and female students. According to studies, when we look at different location segments, the metropolitan region had greater enrollment rates, whereas rural areas had lower enrollment rates.

Of the overall enrollment in 1998, 50.6% of the students were men and 49.4% were women. The percentage of female enrollment in 2000 was 54 percent of the overall enrollment. The percentage of female pupils climbed to 56% in that year. However, it is a good piece of news. The sample's selection of schools with a majority of female students was the primary cause of the higher percentage of female enrollment. The establishment of the female stipend program and tuition price waiver, particularly in rural areas, was the primary cause of these significant variations in participation rates between male and female. Global organizations have underlined that educating girls is essential for a country's development and for the full potential of its inhabitants. The World Bank website sample also aids in reminding us of the importance of the justification for girls' education.

It is therefore necessary to promote female education so that they may collaborate with men to support the family's economic and advance to success. The good news is that the government has already started providing rural female children with free education up to high school. However, it is important to inform them of the program implemented for their wellbeing. In this matter, many Non-Government Organizations (NGO) and urban students can play a role to urge those unprivileged girls to educate themselves.

Gender Gap in Education of Bangladesh

Gender Gap in Primary Education and Its Size Bangladesh has made significant progress in elementary level education as a result of numerous financial measures and the policy of obligatory primary education. The primary schools now have a gross enrolment percentage of almost 97 percent. However, the results of certain small-scale research indicate that the gross enrolment rate has already surpassed 100%. Bangladeshi Women's Empowerment Through Education 44 Net enrolment rate, however, is close to 87. It's interesting to see that

girls enlist at a higher rate than guys. As a result, in 2002, the gender gap in primary education was almost entirely closed. Gender equality in elementary school has been considerably aided by the programs “food for education,” “cash for education,” and “free books,” all of which have been included in the education budget from the fiscal year 1993–1994. However, only around half of the students enrolling in the program complete it. From 2005 to 2007, the dropout rate was 47.2%; from 2007 to 2018, it was 50.5%. The degree to which there is a gender gap in secondary and higher education In Bangladesh, emphasis has also been placed on enhancing the quality of secondary and higher secondary education through advancements in science and technological education. In our nation, emphasis has been placed on educating students in information and communication technologies. Currently, there are 7651 secondary and upper secondary level madrasah¹⁹, 2427 general colleges, and 16,166 secondary schools. The number of students has risen over time at each of these institutions. According to a survey, the number of pupils enrolled in secondary level schools (Class V to Class X) increased by roughly 21% between 1998 and 2002. It is really heartening to see that girl students enroll at a far higher rate than boy students at secondary level schools. The proportion of female pupils has risen by roughly 26%. It is interesting to note that whereas girls made up slightly more than 51% of secondary school students in 1998, they made up nearly 54% of secondary school students in 2002. This demonstrates that the gender gap in secondary education has more than just shrunk; it has been constructed against boys.

Size of the Gender Gap in Higher Education The number of students enrolled in tertiary institutions of higher learning has likewise grown over time. Similar to primary and secondary levels of education, the number of private colleges and universities as well as their enrolment have increased quickly. A rising number of students may have been drawn to private universities by the assurance of completing the courses of study within the allotted time, the politics-free environment in contrast to public universities, and other factors. There are more female students overall in colleges and universities at private institutions, which may be due to the same factor.

The number of students enrolling in higher education is still quite low. In Bangladesh, just 7 students out of every 1000 enroll in higher education (Society & Change Vol. VI, No. 4, October–December 2012 45). For female students, this percentage is significantly lower. As a result, the gender gap in tertiary education continues to be very large. There are 61:39 male and female students enrolled in tertiary education. Female students in postsecondary madrasah education have climbed by 40%, whilst female students in tertiary general education have increased by only 21%, indicating an even worse gender imbalance in this level of education. Female enrolment rates at public colleges were 25 percent in 2008, 27 percent in 2009, 28 percent in 2010, and 27.15 percent in 2011, according

to the University Grants Commission's²² (UGC) annual reports.

The Impact of Women's Education in Society

Education of Women's Role in National Development benefits education range widely, including improvements in housing, clothing, food, health, transportation, communication, entertainment, and the profitable use of leisure time. The vast majority of our female population's education would significantly advance their capacity for personal growth. Husbands and kids stand to benefit greatly as well. Women are more inclined to believe in themselves and their capacity to make valuable contributions to the growth of the country.

Education aids help women in fulfilling their marital responsibilities. A married lady is supposed to look after her household, including her husband and kids. She is expected to cook, clean, and raise her children with whatever knowledge and abilities she possesses.

Mothers have a significant role in ensuring the children's excellent health, which benefits the entire community and country as a whole. Starting in the womb, one can achieve good health. It begins with the expectant mother being aware of what constitutes a balanced diet, abstaining from harmful medicines, and taking steps detrimental to the health of the unborn child. If a woman is educated, she can be aware of all these dangerous factors.

Women who are educated will be able to contribute to the establishment and reconstruction of nations. A few women presently hold prominent posts in Bangladesh, including those of Prime Minister, Leader of the Opposition in the Parliament, Speaker, and Deputy Leader, as well as some ministerial roles, particularly those related to international affairs and the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court. Final thoughts and suggestions are that the progress of a country must include the empowerment of women. Since women make up half of the population, progress is impossible without completely taking into consideration their wants and interests.

In truth, a country's strength lies in its empowered women. It makes sense to assume that progress will boost women's status because it improves the living conditions of society as a whole. Nobody in Bangladesh can complete the process of emancipating and empowering women in a short amount of time. But women have taken advantage of their opportunities and advanced significantly. At 48 distinct Empowerment of Women through Education in Bangladesh events, the Bangladeshi government expressed an official desire to better the lives of women. Here, education has been crucial to the emancipation of women. There is still work to be done in the domain of women's education despite all the efforts made by the various levels of government, together with non-governmental organizations and donor agencies.

Decrease of women enrollment in Higher Education

Bangladesh has shown progress with women's education thus far. At the basic and secondary levels, girls continue

to outnumber boys and make up more than half of student enrollment.

When it comes to college and university, though, things change significantly. The latest government data show that females' enrollment starts to decline at the college level and that the trend continues as they progress to higher education.

According to data compiled by the Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information and Statistics (Banbeis), in 2020, 55.41 percent of girls were enrolled in junior school, which is sixth through eighth grade, while 40.78 percent of them were enrolled in master's-level coursework. Girls made up 53.57 percent of all secondary students in the ninth and tenth grades, whereas their share dropped to 43.80 percent at the graduation level. The situation was nearly identical in 2018 and 2019.

The gloomy numbers do have one positive aspect. In the three years leading up to 2020, the proportion of women pursuing master's degrees has grown. According to the Banbeis data, around 36.70 percent of female students enrolled in master's level courses in 2019.

Education experts discussed this diminishing trend and pointed out that child marriage and poverty are the main causes. The role of sexual harassment on the journey to and from college and university is equally significant. In addition, they claimed that in addition to the lack of reliable transportation, the lack of girls' hostels is a barrier to girls' education. Experts claimed that the prolonged closure of educational facilities brought on by Covid-19 had made things worse.

Only 37.50 percent of the 1,12,779 female students enrolled in 43 public colleges have access to dormitories, according to University Grants Commission data. There are no dormitories at Jagannath University for the 6,583 female students. At Barishal University, about 14% of female students could use the dorms, and 30% at Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology could get housing (Buet). There is a severe lack of dorm space in girls' colleges. There are 22,000 students enrolled at Eden Mahila College, but only 6,000 of them can fit in the college's six dorms, according to principal Supriya Bhattacharya. Prof. Tania Haque of the department of women's and gender studies at Dhaka University stressed the need of infrastructure like female-only dorms as well as safety when traveling to and from educational facilities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We can now state with certainty that there is a gender disparity at all educational levels. Additionally, it is clear that when education levels rise, the gender disparity widens. Since decision-making reaches the core of patriarchy, which supports male dominance over resources and institutions of state and family, it has the greatest impact on empowering women. Women's ability to make decisions is largely influenced by their level of education. As a result, it is anticipated that as women's educational levels rise, so will their ability to make decisions and their access to political power at all

levels—at the state, institutional, and family levels. For instance, the Union Parishad elections in 1997 and 2002 significantly altered the participation of women in politics and decision-making.

13,000 women joined the Union Parishad and became members. However, it is upsetting to learn that 20% of the female members are uneducated. Between 2 and 6, there are very few women in the cabinet, which is the highest decision-making body in the nation. There are now 70 members of parliament (MP), 50 of which are reserved seats. Recently, a woman MP was chosen to serve as Speaker of the House. In the Supreme Court's Appellate Division, there is only one Justice. The last three decades of Bangladesh's political history have seen little change in this position, despite the fact that women's educational advancement has been notable during this time. Women are hardly present in other areas where decisions are made, such as the bureaucracy and high-level positions Empowerment of Women through Education in Bangladesh 46. According to recent data, there are only two women among the 70 secretaries and 11 among the 243 additional secretaries. Currently, the nation lacks a female deputy commissioner (DC) (Ministry of Public Administration, April, 2013).

Research Findings

1. Poverty, which causes parents to favor their sons as children.
2. The attitude of society and parents toward girls' education remains demotivating.
3. A big issue for female education is early marriage. Consequently, the girls are not motivated to attend school.
4. Eve-teasing issues affecting girls.
5. Social inequality is a problem that affects girls.
6. Residential facilities in colleges and universities are problematic for girls.

Limitations of the study

Mainly due to time Limitation, I was not able to make the study much informative, resourceful, elaborate and analytical as I intended to. Due to my workload and studies for my thesis paper I could not avail much time for further research on this paper.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Community guardians and educators should inspire female students.
2. The government and community should inspire and raise awareness among students, both boys and girls, about how to solve this issue.
3. The government and political figures should take action to lessen socioeconomic inequality.
4. The government and relevant authorities shall guarantee a residential facility for female students. In order for them to continue studying more.
5. In order to lower the degree of poverty among parents, poverty alleviation measures should be clearly stated, aggressively pursued, and objectively carried out. This

will make it possible for parents to provide their kids with equal educational chances.

6. The National Education Policy's provisions relating to equal opportunity for all Bangladeshis should be faithfully implemented.

7. Political leaders play a critical role in the problem of women's emancipation. Our leaders must demonstrate via genuine action that they are genuinely interested in using effective initiatives to address this issue. Whatever plans are started, they should be carried out completely and routinely reviewed.

8. Women should be represented on curriculum boards to help identify and eliminate any potential gender biases that may exist.

9. More pro-women policies should focus on empowering women via education.

10. Appropriate educational research groups and governmental departments must start and support ongoing study into the variables influencing women's educational opportunities.

11. Women must organize themselves to meet the challenges of a positive and meaningful role in the struggle for national emancipation, development, and progress through the acquisition of functional education that will usher in the future.

12. In service and pre-service education of teachers should be developed, helping the teachers develop skills to combat stereotyping and raise awareness of the constraints that gender stereotyping imposes on the development of young girls.

13. The government ought to provide more possibilities for women in order to pique their interest in education.

14. Last but not least, government should take all the necessary steps for the proper utilization of foreign aid in the education sector.

CONCLUSION

Napoleon once reportedly quipped, "Give me a learned mother, and I'll guarantee you the birth of a civilized and learned nation." Islam in our country has placed a strong emphasis on women's education. A nation's success largely depends on how well-educated its people are. It is claimed that a country's foundation is its educational system. Early marriage is the most frequent obstacle to the implementation of female education. Additionally, some individuals and groups attempt to refute religion with spurious religious justifications. Women make up roughly half of the overall population in our nation. A nation cannot become prosperous by excluding such a sizable portion of its inhabitants. Everything in life cannot be accomplished solely by men. From this angle, female education is essential. First off, it is true that women have unique responsibilities and obligations for their families. She has a lot of roles to play well. In the same family, a woman might be both the mother and the wife. She has a lot of roles to play well. In the same family, a woman might be both the mother and the wife. For her to fully carry out her role, she must overcome numerous

challenges. To carry out their responsibilities effectively, education is essential. Second, every female is capable of becoming a mother. A child's mother has a significant impact on their education. An educated mother would be able to raise her child appropriately by instilling in them the moral principles she learned while continuing her education. Thirdly, men and women should bear social obligations equally. A woman can support her spouse in every aspect of life when they are married. She can work and make money so the spouse isn't under as much strain. Consequently, it is crucial that women have an education. The government has incorporated topics like cooking, child rearing, home economics, etc. into the curriculum to support female education. However, it appears to be quite a distance to travel.

In addition, women in today's culture are treated quite poorly. Women should be taught in order to protect our female population from unplanned negligence. Still today, there are many who are vehemently opposed to female education. They believe that a woman's only responsibility is to take care of the home and raise her children. A strong woman has the sole ability to educate the entire country. As a result, we are unable to imagine the advancement of our nation without the education of women. For the benefit of the nation, all essential measures should be done to promote female education.

In many rural areas of Bangladesh, there is currently little to no focus placed on the education of girls. Contrarily, the female education system in rural areas is disregarded and is still in its primitive state although the country as a whole is progressing by meeting specific target parameters. Without a doubt, Bangladesh has made significant advancements in girls' education, for which Bangladesh currently serves as a role model in South Asia.

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